

Synchronization and Harmonization of Corruption Prevention Models in Indonesia

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Abstract

This study describes the synchronization and harmonization of the corruption prevention model according to the United Nations Convention Against Corruption, and the corruption prevention model by the Corruption Eradication Commission in Indonesia. The scope of research focuses on the study of the United Nations Convention Against Corruption Convention document and the Corruption Eradication Commission Law. The data collection method is done by interview and documentation. The results show that the corruption eradication model by the Corruption Eradication Commission has synchronization and harmonization with the United Nations Convention Against Corruption Convention, this study shows an interesting fact that the corruption eradication model in Law No. 19 of 2019 concerning the Commission to Eradicate the Commission, provides institutional strengthening in eradicating corruption in Indonesia, especially the formation of a supervisory board appointed by the president, in overseeing the implementation of the duties and powers of the corruption eradication commission

Introduction

Corruption is a crime that has been considered an extraordinary crime, "extra ordinary crime", a concern over the seriousness of the problem and the threat posed by corruption to the stability and security of society that damages institutional institutions and democratic values, ethical values and justice as well as disrupting sustainable development and law enforcement, corruption is no longer a local problem, but an international phenomenon that affects the whole society and economy, corruption even weakens the foundations of the nation and is a common enemy of all countries in the world.

Corruption eradication in Indonesia is institutionally carried out by the Corruption Eradication Commission as regulated in Law Number 19 of 2019, by taking various comprehensive and multidisciplinary approaches to prevent and eradicate corruption effectively, therefore in this study the question is (a) whether there is synchronization and harmonization of the United Nations Convention Against Corruption Convention on the Corruption Eradication Commission Law in Indonesia. (b) how to synchronize and harmonize the Convention with the existing legal system in Indonesia with the United Nations Convention Against Corruption Convention. The novelty of the information obtained from the results of this study is that the Corruption Eradication Commission in Indonesia synchronizes and harmonizes the United Nations Convention Against Corruption Convention with the Corruption Eradication Commission Law, in a model of corruption eradication which is carried out professionally, intensively and continuously. To avoid corruption, therefore the corruption eradication model in the United Nations Convention Against Corruption Convention and the Corruption Eradication Commission Law, increasingly gives a new color to corruption eradication by involving various elements, as well as strengthening institutions within the Corruption Eradication Commission.

The involvement of various elements in the eradication of corruption has also been explained by several countries in articles and journals. (1), the Journal "The Regionalization of the fight against Corruption In Italy" shows that in the context of regionalization of corruption eradication, it is necessary to create synchronization with national decision-making centers in order to work symbiotically by formulating important steps; this includes compiling a regional anti-corruption plan which is implemented at the regional level and must be implemented in the region with involvement at the provincial and city levels. (2) The article "Preventing Corruption In Turkey; explains that the need for a series of strong, continuous and synchronous policies and actions to promote public integrity, transparency and accountability as well as to prevent and punish corrupt practices in public life has become increasingly significant. In a journal review This is the need to create a

coalition between (politicians) clean, competent (bureaucrats), and competitive (businessmen) to wage an effective and long-lasting war against corruption. Comparing the three coalition members with three core issues, namely the political financing regime, the public personnel regime, and a sensible public expenditure and procurement regime, create or maintain competition (business people) to wage an effective and lasting war against corruption. (3) The article "Corruption In Kazakhstan and The Quality of Governance in this article explains that in creating quality the government of various Yan businesses g is carried out in the disclosure of various corruption scandals, but behind the actions in fighting corruption there is a serious and systematic phenomenon, namely the most endemic form of corruption is the various transfers of funds within the structure of the state and national companies which remain unclear and remain unaccountable. (4) Journal "The Significance of Holistic approach Application in the politics of Corruptive activities the challenges of Serbia explains the importance of an integrated approach (holistic is a strategic asset in realizing anti-corruption action. The active role of the state and its responsibility in eradicating corruption) is an important part of the platform. new transitions, moral and ethical issues of the ruler are very important to the success of the transition. the need for reform in the country given contemporary theory and practice, solutions to the challenges of corruption are seen from a new institutional perspective. (5) Journal of Public Administration, Finance and Law. "A Critical analysis of whistleblower protection in the European Union "explains that whistleblower protection is an important anti-corruption instrument. Countries around the world including European Union countries have tried differently with the system of protecting public employees who disclose information that leads to investigations and prosecutions for corruption. The analysis suggests that the success of eradicating public sector corruption depends on the protection of whistleblowers, especially in countries where public sector corruption is systematic and endemic, such as in the member countries of the Eastern European Union which are considered to be the main whistleblower protection in the European Union, including current good practice" (6) The article The Investment Of The Anti-Corruption Values In Education a Practice, concludes that one of the most effective means of breaking the chain of corruption is the model of eradicating involvement in the closest circle, one of which is strengthening anti-corruption education from an early age. inheritance of noble character and elevation of character. (7) In the article entitled Renewal of the Corruption Eradication Strategy in Indonesia, it is concluded that corruption eradication with current conditions requires government legal politics as legal police regarding the laws that will be enforced in achieving the country's goals.

Literature Review

Characteristics of Corruption

Cambridge Advanced Learner's Dictionary (2003) defines corruption as illegal, immoral or dishonest behavior, especially by people in positions of power. In addition, there are variations in the definition and scope of corruption that tend to vary between scientists (Rose-Ackerman, 1974, 1997; Shleifer and Vishny, 1993; Azariadis and Lahiri, 1997; Klitgaard, 1998; Tanzi, 1998; Teachout, 1999; Bowles, 2000; Del Monte and Papagni, 2001; Jain, 2001; Chang, 2013).

Meanwhile, in the Black's Law Dictionary, corruption is "An act done with an intention to give some advantage inconsistent with official duty and the rights of order. The act on official or fiduciary person who is unlawful and wrongful use his station or character to procure some benefit for himself or for another person contrary to duty and the rights of others. and the rights of the other parties. Actions of an official or trust that violate the law and wrongly use his position or character to get an advantage for himself or for others, contrary to his obligations and the rights of other parties.

According to the Webster Student Dictionary, the oldest corruption in Latin is *corrumpere* which can be interpreted as rottenness, ugliness, depravity, dishonesty, can be bribed, immoral, deviations from chastity, words that are insulting or slander, in the study of corruption crimes together with prostitution is the oldest crime in the world. Corruption in English is corruption or corrupt, in French it is called corruption and in Dutch it is called *corruptie*. Presumably it is from the Dutch that the word corruption is born in Indonesian.

Furthermore, in the crime study there are at least 9 types of corruption. First, political bribery includes power in the legislative field as a law-forming body. Politically controlled by an interest because the funds spent during general elections are often related to the activities of certain companies. Second, political kickbacks, namely activities related to the contract work contract system between implementing officials and entrepreneurs that provide opportunities to bring in a lot of money for the parties concerned. Third, election fraud is corruption that is directly related to general election fraud. Fourth, corrupt campaign practice is the practice of campaigning using state facilities. Fifth, discretionary corruption, namely corruption that is committed because there is freedom to determine policies. Sixth, illegal corruption is corruption committed by confusing legal language or legal interpretation. Seventh, ideological corruption is a combination of discretionary corruption and illegal

corruption committed for group purposes. Eighth, political corruption is the abuse of power or authority entrusted to it for personal gain. Ninth, mercenary corruption, namely the abuse of power solely for personal gain.

In the journal *Rechts Vinding*, Syed Husain Alatas, suggests 7 typologies of corruption:

- (1). Transactive Corruption, namely a type of corruption with a reciprocal agreement.
- (2). Nepotistic corruption
- (3). Extortive corruption or corruption by extortion.
- (4). Investive corruption, namely providing services or goods for the benefit of the future
- (5). Defensive corruption, namely forcing others to be involved in the corruption process.
- (6). Outgenic corruption or corruption done alone.
- (7). Supportive corruption, namely corruption of support.

According to Eddy O.S. Hiariej in one of the articles entitled *United Nations Convention Against Corruption in the criminal law system* qualifies acts that are considered a criminal act of corruption and examines the point of view of criminal law, which refers to the Corruption Eradication Law, is as follows:

- (1). Corruption related to state financial losses.
- (2). Corruption related to bribery.
- (3). Corruption related to embezzlement.
- (4). Corruption related to extortion.
- (5). Corruption related to fraudulent acts.
- (6). Corruption related to procurement.
- (7). Corruption related to gratification.

Corruption is also an action that falls within the scope of international crimes known as the internationalization of corruption crimes. In outline there are two categories of codification of international crimes in various treaties. First, treaties which expressly state acts which are prohibited and declared as crimes under international law. Second, treaties which do not declare prohibited acts as a crime, but instead oblige participating countries to prosecute or extradite the perpetrators of these acts based on national law. As an international crime, there are five certain behaviors that can be categorized as international crimes and if one of them is fulfilled then it can qualify as an international crime. First, prohibited behavior has a significant impact on international interests, in particular international peace and security. Second, prohibited behavior is bad and is considered to threaten the values shared by the world community, including what has been considered by history to be behavior that touches the human conscience. This is supported by many international opinions that bribery in the international sphere must be eradicated. Third, prohibited behavior has transnational implications involving or influencing more than one country in planning, preparing or acting, either through the diversity of nationalities of the perpetrators or victims or the equipment used beyond national borders. Fourth, behavior that endangers the protection of international interests or of people who are protected internationally. Fifth, the behavior violates protected international interests but does not reach the stages mentioned in the first and second points, but because of its nature, such behavior can be prevented and suppressed through international criminalization[†].

In the context of corruption crimes by referring to the United Nations Convention Against Corruption Convention, the category of codification of the internationalization of corruption crimes includes treaties that do not declare prohibited acts as an international crime, but oblige participating countries to prosecute or extradite the perpetrators of these acts based on national law. . as stated in article 30 of the United Nations Convention Against Corruption Convention.

In the background paper of the United Nations Convention Against Corruption. describes the impact of corruption crimes the background for the crime of corruption, namely; corruption is considered to damage democracy, corruption is considered to destroy the rule of law, corruption can interfere with sustainable development, corruption is considered to damage the market, corruption can damage the quality of life, corruption violates human rights. This is related to the rights to a decent life for the community but is neglected because the state does not have enough budget to improve people's welfare due to corruption[‡].

Based on the impact described as a result of corruption, the United Nations Convention Against Corruption organization aims to prevent and eradicate corruption efficiently and effectively, international cooperation in technical assistance including the return of criminal assets, integrity and accountability as well as transparency and proper management in the public sector.

In national law, the criminal act of corruption as regulated in Law Number 20 of 2001 jo. Law Number 31 Year 1999 concerning Eradication of Corruption Crime. The elements of the criminal act of corruption consist of: ▪ "... doing something against the law enriches oneself or another person or a corporation which can harm the state finances or the country's economy" (Article 2) What is meant by "unlawfully" in this Article includes acts against the law in a formal sense as well as in a material sense, that is, even though the act is not regulated in

statutory regulations, if the act is considered despicable because it is not in accordance with the sense of justice. or the norms of social life in society, then the act can be punished. In this provision, the word "can" before the phrase "detrimental to the country's finances or economy" indicates that a criminal act of corruption is a formal offense, that is, the existence of a criminal act of corruption is sufficient by fulfilling the elements of the act that have been formulated without the consequence. ▪ "... with the aim of benefiting oneself or another person or a corporation, abusing the authority, opportunity or means available to it because of the position or position that could harm the state finances or the state economy" (Article 3).

Further, in Law Number 8 of 2010 concerning the prevention and eradication of the crime of money laundering (UU TPPU), the criminal act of corruption can be accumulated with the crime of money laundering.

Based on the above description, a definition of corruption can be formulated, which is any act that is against the law with the aim of enriching (benefiting) oneself or another person or a corporation, abusing the authority, opportunity or means available to it because of the position or position that can harm finances. country or the country's economy.

Principles of corruption eradication

In the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia Article 1, paragraph 3, it is explained that the State of Indonesia is a constitutional state. The consequence as a rule of law means that all aspects of life in the nation and state are in accordance with the law, including acts of corruption that have caused losses to the State⁸. Therefore, related to the problem of corruption cases, various policies carried out by the government, namely the issuance of Law Number 31 of 1999 concerning the Eradication of Corruption Crimes, as amended by Law number 20 of 2001. Subsequently issued a presidential instruction (Inpres)) Number 5 of 2004 concerning the Acceleration of Corruption Eradication, Presidential Instruction Number 17 of 2011 concerning the Acceleration of Corruption Eradication in 2012, Inpres 17 of 2011 concerning the Acceleration of Corruption Eradication in 2012, Presidential Instruction Number 1 of 2013 concerning the Action Plan for the Prevention and Eradication of Corruption, Inpres Number 2 of 2014 concerning Action to Prevent and Eradicate Corruption in 2014, and the last is Presidential Instruction Number 10 of 2016 concerning Preventive and Eradication Actions Corruption in 2016 and 2017 and the most recent Law is Law Number 19 of 2019 concerning the second amendment to Law Number 30 of 2002. Concerning the Corruption Eradication Commission.

The prevention and eradication of criminal acts of corruption globally is regulated in the United Nations Convention Against Corruption, 2003 (United Nations Against Corruption), In 2003, the United Nations (UN) established the Convention Against Corruption (United Nations Convention Against Corruption) which aims to prevent corruption globally by conducting international cooperation to jointly take steps to eliminate corruption around the world. The UN's attention to the problem of corruption can be seen since 2000. The 55th UN General Assembly produced UN Resolution 55/61 on December 6 2000. This resolution states the need to formulate an international legal instrument against corruption globally. This international legal instrument is indispensable. to bridge different legal systems and at the same time advance efforts to eradicate corruption in an effective manner. This is because the problem of corruption has now crossed national borders, this is stated in the fourth paragraph of the preamble to the United Nations Convention Against Corruption Convention**.

"Convince that corruption is no longer local matter but a transnational phenomenon that affects all societies and economies, making international cooperation to prevent and control it essential."

Then after going through several sessions and meetings, the UN General Assembly finally accepted the United Nations Convention Against Corruption Convention, which was ratified by a High Level Conference (Summit) on 9-11 December 2003 in Merida, Mexico. Until 2010, a total of 141 states parties have signed this convention and it has even been ratified by 145 countries. Since its ratification in 2003, many countries have used the mechanisms and principles contained in the United Nations Convention Against Corruption Convention to deal with corruption problems in their respective countries. One of the 145 countries that ratified the *United Nations Convention Against Corruption* Convention is Indonesia, which ratified the *United Nations Convention Against Corruption* Convention on 18 April 2006 through Law Number 7 of 2006.

There are several objectives of the United Nations Convention Against Corruption, namely: First, increasing and strengthening measures to prevent and eradicate corruption more efficiently and effectively. Second, improve, facilitate and support international cooperation and technical assistance in efforts to prevent and eradicate corruption, including asset recovery, and third, improve integrity, accountability and proper and correct management of problems and public wealth.

What is quite significant in this convention is that the provisions of the convention emphasize that the state is obliged to develop and implement or maintain an effective and coordinated anti-corruption policy by increasing

public participation and reflecting the principles of law enforcement, good management of public affairs and public wealth, integrity, transparency and accountability, and therefore the state must endeavor to establish and promote effective practices for the purpose of preventing corruption. Indonesia as a rule of law has certainly followed up by ratifying Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 7 of 2006 concerning the Ratification of the United Nations Convention Against Corruption. and then these provisions are followed up by Law number 19 of 1999 concerning the second amendment to law 30 of 2002 concerning the Corruption Eradication Commission, this shows that the eradication of corruption in Indonesia clearly and clearly gives authority to the Eradication Commission. Corruption.

Method

The research method is descriptive qualitative with normative juridical analysis, the data used are primary data and secondary data. Primary data is in the form of interviews, while secondary material is in the form of laws and other statutory regulations as well as other library materials such as articles in journals, both published in book form and on the internet. Besides that, it also uses tertiary materials in the form of a dictionary, all these materials are studied carefully and then presented in the form of data in the form of descriptions, then the data is analyzed qualitatively to answer problems in the research, so that it can be a conclusion

Results and Discussion

The results of this study explain the policies and practices of corruption prevention models in Indonesia which refer to the provisions of the United Nations Convention Against Corruption convention and the Corruption Eradication Commission Law, and explain in detail the relationship or synchronization and harmonization of these two provisions.

The United National Convention Against Corruption Convention is one of the most important international instruments in the context of preventing and eradicating corruption effectively with a comprehensive and multidisiplinary principle or approach. Indonesia as a country that has participated in ratifying the United Nations Convention Against Corruption convention, morally is also the most important part in implementing strategies in preventing and eradicating corruption crimes. The Corruption Eradication Commission Law as a national instrument gives authority to the Corruption Eradication Commission as one of the institutions that handles corruption cases on the principle of equal authority and protection of human rights.

Prevention and eradication of corruption is the responsibility of all states and that states must cooperate with one another, with the support and involvement of individuals and groups outside the public sector, such as civil society, non-governmental organizations and civil society organizations to make efforts in this area can be effective, adhering to the principles of sound management of public affairs and public wealth, justice, responsibility and equality before the law and the need to maintain integrity and to promote a culture of resistance to corruption. Several important things are regulated in the United Nations Convention Against Corruption and Corruption Eradication Commission Law in the corruption prevention strategy.

The following table describes the synchronization and harmonization of provisions in the United National Convention Against Corruption convention with the Corruption Eradication Commission Law,

TABLE 1.

Analysis of Article 5, United Nations Convention Against Corruption Convention with Articles 6 and 15 of the Corruption Eradication Commission Law.

United Nations Convention Against Corruption Convention. Article 5	Law on the Corruption Eradication Commission. Article 6
States are obliged, in accordance with the basic principles of their legal systems, to develop and implement or maintain an effective and coordinated anti-corruption policy that enhances public participation and reflects the principles of law enforcement, management of public affairs of agencies tasked with providing public services, transparency and accountability	In article 6, letter b. It is emphasized that the Corruption Eradication Commission in its task is to coordinate with agencies authorized to eradicate corruption crimes and agencies in charge of implementing public services One of the efforts of the Indonesian government in synchronizing and harmonizing the United Nations

	Convention Against Corruption Convention, in law enforcement is to strengthen the institution of the corruption eradication commission which is more independent, transparent and more accountable, therefore in Law Number 19 of 2019 concerning the corruption eradication commission . a Supervisory Board formed by the President in order to oversee the implementation of duties and powers with the corruption eradication commission
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Source: Document Analysis

From the two provisions above, it shows that to eradicate corruption, efforts should be made for coordination and joint cooperation in eradicating corruption, by involving various elements. so that it will be possible to achieve effective eradication.

The corruption eradication strategy by the Corruption Eradication Commission in the field of prevention has used a preventive strategy by making system improvements. The system applied in Indonesia provides opportunities for criminal acts of corruption. this system can minimize the occurrence of criminal acts of corruption. These system improvements include:

- (1). Encouraging transparency in state administration, as has been done by the Corruption Eradication Commission in receiving reports on the Wealth of State Administrators (LHKPN) as well as gratuities. The model or strategy as stipulated separately in article 7 states that in carrying out the task of preventing the Corruption Eradication Commission, it shall register and examine the assets of state administrators, as well as receive reports and determine the status of gratuities. One of the prevention of criminal acts of corruption in Indonesia is to improve the system, by encouraging transparency of state administrators, as has been done by the Corruption Eradication Commission. The following is data on the level of compliance of state administrators in reporting LHKPN as follows:

TABLE 2.
Level Of Reporting Compliance 2019 State Official Property Report

Field	Compulsory Reporting	Already Report	Yet Not Reported.	Obedience
Executive.	269.355	202,303	67,052	75,11%
Judicative	23,710	14,478	9,232	61, 05%
People's Consultative Assembly.	8	6	2	75,00%
House Of Representatives	554	313	241	56,50%
Regional Representative Council	132	100	32	75,76%
People's Representative Assembly.	17,631	10,653	6,978	60,42%
State Owned Business Agency / Regional Owned Business Agency	28,376	25,364	3,012	89,39%

Source: Report of the Chairman of the Corruption Eradication Commission in Kompas TV 1 April 2019.

Based on the data above, it shows that the reporting system for the Wealth Report of State Officials to the Corruption Eradication Commission seems that this effort has not shown an optimal level of reporting from state officials. However, this is an effort by the Corruption Eradication Commission to minimize corruption.

- (2). Provide recommendations to related ministries and agencies to take corrective steps. Improvements through this system actually have to be more emphasized on the matter of reforming the system and management which can minimize opportunities and opportunities to commit corrupt practices. The program for reforming the system and management may be suitable if it is optimized by giving special assignments to the state secretariat and the ministry of state apparatus utilization. Observing this strategy, in line with what was directed by Susilo Bambang Yodoyono when he was President of the Republic of Indonesia, he emphasized that in order to prevent corruption from occurring, communication and coordination between law enforcers is highly needed and prioritized.
- (3). Modernizing online public services and an integrated monitoring system to make it more transparent and accountable. According to Laode M Syarif, there are four main things that the Corruption Eradication Commission has done for prevention. First, efforts to improve the procurement of goods and services in the government, so that they are more accountable and transparent. According to the Corruption Eradication Commission, this sector is prone to corruption. Syarif asked the procurement of goods and services to use e-procurement services to be accountable and transparent. His party stated that he was helping regions that did not yet have an e-catalog program. Therefore, Syarif asked all regional governments to have e-proc, plus the e-catalog to be accelerated, so that cost increases would not occur. is a Whistleblower system. This system can be an effort to report cases of corruption in Indonesia, with this system using people from both internal and outside the community to provide reports to the Corruption Eradication Commission and be a good control in prevention efforts, and this system is expected will help the process of dealing with corruption in Indonesia.

Furthermore, in increasing public participation as stipulated in the United Nations Convention Against Corruption convention, as a form of harmonization, the Corruption Eradication Commission with its authority in the field of prevention receives reports and determines the status of gratification as part of its coordination task. Reports referred to in the Corruption Eradication Commission Law are reports from the public and reports from authorized agencies, in order to reflect the principles of law enforcement as emphasized in the United Nations Convention Against Corruption convention.

TABLE 3

Analysis of Article 5, United Nations Convention Against Corruption Convention with Article 15 of the Corruption Eradication Commission Law.

United Nations Convention Against Corruption Convention Article 5	Corruption Eradication Commission Law Article 15
States are obliged, in accordance with the basic principles of their legal systems, to develop and implement or maintain an effective and coordinated anti-corruption policy that enhances public participation and reflects the principles of law enforcement, management of public affairs of agencies tasked with providing public services, transparency and accountability.	<p>Article 15 letter states that the Corruption Eradication Commission is obliged to provide protection for witnesses or reporters who submit reports or provide information regarding the occurrence of criminal acts of corruption in accordance with statutory provisions</p> <p>Article 15 above shows that there is synchronization and harmonization with the legal system in Indonesia to provide protection for witnesses and reporters as stipulated in Law Number 13 Tahun 2006 concerning the protection of witnesses and victims.</p>

Source: Document Analysis

After observing the Corruption Eradication Commission Law in article 15 that the Corruption Eradication Commission with its inherent obligations in carrying out its duties is based on the principle of legal certainty. Furthermore, in terms of good management of public affairs and public wealth, integrity, transparency and accountability. as regulated in the United Nations Convention Against Corruption, the Corruption Eradication

Commission Law also explicitly coordinates and receives reports from agencies that carry out public services related to the presence of symptoms or the occurrence of corruption. The Corruption Eradication Commission in carrying out its duties and authorities adheres to the principles; legal certainty, openness, accountability, public interest, proportionality; and respect for human rights. As stated in article 5 of the Corruption Eradication Commission Law

TABLE 4.

Analysis of Article 5, United Nations Convention Against Corruption Convention with other policies on Corruption Eradication.

United Nations Convention Against Corruption Convention	Indonesian government policy
<p>Article 5, paragraph 2, States parties shall endeavor to establish and promote effective practices for the purpose of preventing corruption.</p> <p>Article 5. Paragraph 3. Affirms that state parties are obliged to make every effort to evaluate legal instruments and related administrative measures on a regular basis so that they are adequate to prevent and eradicate corruption</p> <p>Article 5 paragraph 4 states that the State needs to cooperate with other countries and with relevant international and regional organizations to enhance and develop efforts to prevent corruption</p>	<p>Indonesia has a commitment to the G20 as the world's premier economic forum that agrees on anti-corruption principles on certain specific issues.</p> <p>Corruption prevention policies and practices in Indonesia have given birth to various policies or regulations in the eradication of criminal acts of corruption. One of the latest regulations in efforts to prevent and eradicate corruption is the issuance of Law Number 19 of 2019 concerning the Second Amendment to Law Number 30 of 2002 concerning the Corruption Eradication Commission.</p> <p>The President of the Republic of Indonesia launched a regulation, namely Presidential Regulation Number 54 of 2018 concerning a national strategy for preventing corruption. Through this national strategy, it is hoped that it will be more focused, measured and oriented towards the results and impacts felt by this nation. This strategy is a form of collaboration between various agencies which is expected to facilitate coordination in the context of realizing the action plan to prevent corruption</p> <p>Corruption Eradication Commission Law. Article 7 letters c, d, e are clear and unequivocal that the Corruption Eradication Commission is in carrying out its preventive duties. The Corruption Eradication Commission is authorized; organizing anti-corruption education programs in every educational network, planning and implementing socialization programs for the eradication of corruption crimes, conducting anti-corruption campaigns to the public; as part of efforts to develop and improve effective practices for the purpose of preventing corruption and article 7 letter f of the Law. The Corruption Eradication Commission with its task is to carry out bilateral and multilateral cooperation in eradicating criminal acts of corruption</p>

Source: Documentary Analysis

TABLE 5.

Analysis of the United Nations Convention Against Corruption Article 6 with Article 7 of the Corruption Eradication Commission Law

The following table provides an overview of the synchronization and harmonization of the provisions of article 6 of The United Nations Convention Against Corruption Convention with Article 7 of the Corruption Eradication Commission Law.

Konvensi United Nations Convention Against Corruption	Corruption Eradication Commission Law
<p>Article 6 emphasizes that corruption prevention agencies, the state is obliged to comply with the basic principles of its legal system, seek the existence of a body or bodies, if deemed necessary, which prevent corruption by means of such as:</p> <p>(a) Implementing the policy and if deemed necessary, supervising and coordinating the implementation of the policy; (b) Increase and disseminate knowledge about corruption prevention</p> <p>Article 6 paragraph 1 also emphasizes the need for the independence of bodies or bodies in carrying out their functions effectively and free from undue influence.</p>	<p>The provisions of this convention are the most important part of the duties and powers of the Corruption Eradication Commission as stipulated in article 7 of the Corruption Eradication Commission Law.</p> <p>Corruption Eradication Commission Law. He affirms that the Corruption Eradication Commission is an institution or an authorized body, in article 3 it is emphasized that the Corruption Eradication Commission is a state institution in the executive power clump which in carrying out its duties and powers is independent and free from the influence of any power.</p>

Source; Document Analysis

In the United Nations Convention Against Corruption convention in outline in its articles it regulates several provisions clearly and firmly in an effort to prevent the occurrence of criminal acts of corruption. These provisions are as follows:

- (1). Establishment of an anti-corruption agency. (article 6)
 - (2). Increased transparency in campaign financing for elections and political parties. (Article 7 paragraph 3)
 - (3). Promotion of efficiency and transparency of public services. (article 7 public sector)
 - (4). Recruitment or acceptance of public services (civil servants) and they are carried out based on merit. (Article 7 paragraph 1 letter e)
 - (5) There is a code of ethics that is designated for public services (civil servants) and they must comply with the code of ethics. (Article 8 paragraph 3)
 - (6). Transparency and accountability of public finances. (article paragraph 2)
 - (7). Application of disciplinary and criminal acts for corrupt civil servants (Article 8 paragraph 6)
 - (8). The creation of special requirements, especially in the public sector which is very vulnerable, such as the judiciary and the public procurement sector. (chapters 9 and 11)
 - (9). Promotion and enforcement of public service standards (article 7 paragraph 1)
 - (10). There is the participation of all components of society in efforts to prevent effective corruption. (Article 13)
- Observe the United Nations Convention Against Corruption convention, 2003 and the provisions in Law Number 19 of 2019 concerning the second amendment to Law Number 30 of 2002 concerning the Corruption Eradication Commission. Observing the two provisions above, it shows that the eradication of criminal acts of corruption emphasizes the prevention of corruption.

Conclusion

The conclusions from the results of this study are presented as follows that the Indonesian Government has ratified the United Nations Convention Against Corruption with Law Number 7 of 2006. Until now, the Corruption Eradication Commission law has synchronized and harmonized with this convention, because of the corruption that has occurred. In Indonesia, it is so massive that the law on the eradication of criminal acts of corruption, especially the Corruption Eradication Commission Law, is a national instrument that must conform

to international instruments. In this context, the implementation of the United Nations Convention Against Corruption becomes an urgent matter. In addition to eradicating corruption efficiently and effectively, the United Nations Convention Against Corruption Convention requires international cooperation in eradicating corruption. In order to strengthen corruption eradication instruments in Indonesia, in addition to establishing a Corruption Eradication Commission, Corruption Eradication Commission Law No. 19 of 2019

Observe the United Nations Convention Against Corruption Convention, 2003 and the provisions in Law Number 19 of 2019 concerning the Corruption Eradication Commission. The two provisions above, indicate that there is an ideal synchronization and harmonization in the context of eradicating the criminal act of corruption which emphasizes on the aspect of preventing corruption. One of the interesting things in this study is the formation of a supervisory board in the Corruption Eradication Commission Law, in overseeing the implementation of the duties and powers of the corruption eradication commission, so that it will further strengthen the institution of a more independent corruption eradication commission. In addition, the Indonesian government has also made efforts to synchronize and harmonize with the prevailing legal system in Indonesia in various policies and laws and regulations.

The limitations of this research are only in terms of the existence or existence of the corruption eradication commission, which should examine the duties and powers of the police, prosecutors and judiciary in eradicating corruption. However, this research is expected to make a positive contribution in disseminating that the Corruption Eradication Commission in Indonesia in making efforts to prevent corruption, has great seriousness by following up and synchronizing and harmonizing the provisions of the United Nations Convention Against Corruption Convention and is part of the responsibility of the state.

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References

Journal Papers:

- [1]. New Journal European Criminal Law 2014. V.Musacchio. 5(4) 565-570.2014. Sagepub.Com
- [2]Artikel. M.Acar, U Emek -" Prventing Corruption. 164.2011 In Asia,2011. book.google.com
- [3]Artikel. Dossym Satpayev "Corruption in Kazakhtan and the Quality of Governace. Liportal.de 2014
- [4]Journal of Economics. S.KurtoviA, G.JovanoviA " The Significance of Holistic approach Application in the politics of Corruptive activies the challengs of Serbia. Org.Mk.
- [5]Journal of Publik Administration, Finance and Law. Author (s) Ada Popescu. Issue Years 2015.No7 page range 135-140 Published by Editura Tehnopress
- [6]Jurnal . Ninik Indawati The Investment Of The Anti-Corruption Values In Education Practice. N.Indawati@Yahoo.Com University Of Kanjuruhan Malang
- [7]Journal of Legal Studies p-ISSN: 1858-0106 e-ISSN: 2502-3926 Volume 17 Number II Month of November,
- [8]Journal of Juris Opinion. Directorate General of Law and International Treaties, Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia, Volume 13. 2013
- [9]. Journal of Rechts vinding, vol 3, No.3. Des. 2014
- [10]. Journal of Legal Studies p-ISSN: 1858-0106 e-ISSN: 2502-3926 Volume 17 Number II Month of November, 2019 The Renewal of Corruption Eradication Strategy in Indonesia.
- [11]. Journal, Winters, J. A. (2011). Oligarchy and Democracy. Journal of The American Interest Volume VII, 2 Holidays, The American Interest, Washington DC.
- [12].Journal of Yolles, Maurice & Sawagvudcharee, O. (2015). Understanding Corruption. Journal of Organizational Transformation & Social Change.
- [13]. Journal .Black's Law Dictionary, Ninth Edition West Thomson reuters business 2009, adapted from the journal Rechts Vinding.Vol.3.No.3 December 2014.
- [14]. Journal . Rajib Sanyal "Determinants of Bribery in International Business. The Cultural and Economic Factors. Journal of Busines Ethcs, vol 59.
- [15]. Jounal. Mimbar Hukum Volume 31, Number 1, February 2019
- [16]. journal ; http://www.unafei.or.jp/english/pdf/RS_No83/No83_20VE_Demostenes2.pdf, quoted in the journal UNP Yogyakarta.
- [17] Journal yuridis.Bambang Waluyo, 2014 Optimization of corruption eradication in Indonesia, Vo.1.No.2 December 2014

- [18] Journal, Legal and development. Rifyal Ka'bah 2007 Corruption in Indonesia Year 37 No.1.
- [19] .Journal MMH. Hariej.O.S. Eddy. Questioning the verdict of the Corruption Court. Volume 4 No.1.Tahun 2013
- [20] Journal. Ninik Indawati The Investment Of The Anti-Corruption Values In Education Practice. N.Indawati@Yahoo.Com University Of Kanjuruhan Malang

Books:

- [21].Andi Hamzah, 1991, Corruption in Indonesia and its Solution, PT. Gramedia Pustaka UTama, Jakarta,
- [22] Brian L.Cutler (Editor).2008. Encyclopedia of Psychologi and Law.Sage Fublication. Los Angeles, London, New Delhi, Sinagpore.
- [23]Chryssikos, Demostenes, (2010) "Unodc Activities In Promoting And Facilitating The Ratification And Implementation Of The United Nations Convention Against Corruption"
- [24]. Fockemma, S.J. Andreae, 1951 Rechtsgeleerd Handwoordenboek, Groningen-Djakarta: Bij J.B.Wolter Uitgeversmaatschappij N.V as quoted by Andi Hamzah, 1984, Corruption in Indonesia Problems and Solutions, Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- [25]. Heather Strang & John Braithwaite (Editor) Restorative Justice Philosopy To Practice, Asghate Darmouth. Aldershot Buildington USA-Singapore-Sidney,2000.
- [26] Lawrance M.Friedman. The Legal Sistem, A Sosial Science Perspective.Russel Sage Foundation.New York. 1987
- [27]._____.2001 American Law An Introduction . PT Tata Nusa Jakarta
- [28]. Rene David & John E.C.Brierley.1985. Major legal System In The World Today. London. Stevens and Sons.
- [29] Willciam.W.Fisher III, Morton J.Horwitz, Thomas A.Reed. 1993. American Legal Realism. Oxford University Press.

Proceedings Papers

- [30].Proceedings International Seminar FoE (Faculty of Education) - Vol. 1 May 2016
- [31].Background paper United Nations Convention Against Corruption Declaration Of 8 International Compreance Against Corruption In Lima Peru On 7-11 September 1997
- [32].Indonesia's Commitment Book To The United Nations Convention Against Corruption (United Nations Convention Against Corruption) And The G20 Anti-Corruption Working Group (Acwg) 2012-2018.
- [33]. Ministry Of Foreign Affairs (2008) United Nations Convention Against Corruption (United Nations Convention against Corruption) 2003, Ministry of Foreign Affairs Republik Indonesia, Jakarta. Quoted from the journal UPN Veteran Yogyakarta. Hikmatul akbar published 2003.
- [34]. Module "How to prevent corruption in corporations: Practices and strategies) Published by: Directorate of Education and Community Services Dwiwarna Building Corruption Eradication Commission.

Legislation / convention / Internet

- [35]. Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia. 1945 year
- [36]. Law Number 20 of 2001 jo. Law Number 31 of 1999
- [37]. Law Number 19 Year 2019
- [38] . Law Number 13 Year 2006 regarding the protection of witnesses and victims
- [39]. United Nations Convention Against corruption, 2003
- [40]. <https://nasional.kompas.com/read/2017/09/17/17480601/Empat-hal-yang-diupusaha-Corruption-Eradication-Commission-to-prevent-corruption?page=all>
- [41]. <http://national.kompas.com/read/2018/12/10/15314821/data-Corruption-Eradication-Commission-the-number-of-corruption-prosecution-in-2018-decreased-by-412-percent>
- [42]. <http://news.detik.com/berita/d-1165474/important-repressive-measures-in-the-eradication-of-corruption>.

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